

THE
GALLIENIELLIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The family Gallieniellidae is known from 10 genera and 68 species and were first grouped with the Gnaphosidae. Only two genera *Austrachelas* Lawrence, 1938 and *Drassodella* Hewitt, 1916 are known from South Africa. Both genera have recently been revised. The ten species of the genus *Austrachelas* are endemic to South Africa. Only two of the species have a wide distribution in South Africa. Three are known only from one sex and therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons and three are known only from the type locality. Only two species are of special concern. *Austrachelas incertus* Lawrence, 1938 have a small restricted distribution range and experiencing ongoing decline in habitat outside of protected areas it is therefore listed as Vulnerable and *Austrachelas wassenaari* Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009 have a small restricted distribution range it is listed as Rare.

The genus *Drassodella* Hewitt, 1916 is represented by 19 species, all endemic to South Africa. Nine of the species are Data Deficient because only one sex is known or their distribution is restricted to the type locality only. Six species have a wide distribution and are Least Concern. Three species have a small restricted distribution and are listed as Rare while one *Drassodella tenebrosa* Lawrence, 1938 qualifies for Endangered under Criterion B due to ongoing loss of habitat to urban expansion, crop cultivation and plantation forestry.

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Drassodella quinquelabecula Photo Peter Webb

FAMILY GALLIENIELLIDAE Millot, 1947

The family Gallieniellidae is known from 10 genera and 68 species (World Spider Catalog 2020) was first placed with the Gnaphosidae. Only two genera are known from South Africa represented by 29 species.

COMMON NAME: Long-Jawed Ground Spiders.

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: small to medium-sized spiders (5-15.3 mm). Colour varies from orange-brown to bright red, yellow to grey or brown and black to cream or white; sometimes with white bands or spots, chevron markings and even colour or tone. Carapace longer than wide; chelicerae moderately to greatly elongated; eyes eight in two rows (4:4); sternum longer than wide; lateral margins rebordered, with small intercoxal sclerites. Abdomen elongate-oval; with anterior spinnerets widely spaced; conical, bearing a small apical segment and multiple rows of cylindrical gland spigots; median spinnerets long and narrow; posterior spinnerets widely spaced; colulus consisting of a few setae. Legs slender with fourth leg longest.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living, agile ground dwellers frequently found associated with ants. They are sampled during active search or with pitfall traps and leaf litter sifting from the Fynbos, Grassland, Forest, Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama and Succulent Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Both genera *Austrachelas* (Haddad et al. 2009) and *Drassodella* (Mbo & Haddad 2019) have been revised.

Austrachelas sp. Photo Caren Neal

Drassodella sp. Photo Charles Haddad

After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué (1997)

GENUS *AUSTRACHELAS* Lawrence, 1938

The genus *Austrachelas* are known from 10 species endemic to South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020). The genus was transferred here from the Corinnidae by Haddad et al. (2009).

COMMON NAME: Austrachelas Long-Jawed Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Austrachelas incertus* Lawrence, 1938

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL: medium to large sized spiders, 4.7–15.3mm. Carapace orange-brown to bright wine-red in colour, paler along midline; carapace raised evenly along midline, sloping sharply posteriorly; eyes in a closely situated group; anterior eye row procurved, posterior eye row straight or very slightly recurved; chelicerae not protruding far beyond anterior margin of carapace; fangs long, directed obliquely, with scrappy setae close to fang base; lateral margins of endites nearly parallel, inner margin with distinctive groove; labium longer than wide; sternum is oval. Abdomen elongate, grey dorsally with cream chevron markings, pale laterally and ventrally; males with short dorsal scutum, absent in females; dorsum with two pairs of sigilla; venter unsclerotised except for post-epigastic sclerites; anterior lateral spinnerets conical, nearly cylindrical, not widely spaced. Legs with densely scopulate anterior metatarsi and tarsi and strongly spined posterior legs, with the prolateral and retrolateral dorsal metatarsal spines in two rows.

LIFESTYLE: Free running ground dwellers. They are usually sampled with visual search, pitfall traps and litter sifting.

TAXONOMIC NOTE: Genus revised by Haddad et al. (2009).

Austrachelas sp. female Photo Peter Webb

Austrachelas bergi Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009

COMMON NAME: Berg's Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Mpumalanga endemic described by Haddad et al. (2009), from a farm near Nelspruit. Recorded from several localities (EOO= 2 287 km²; AOO= 16 km²; 398-1436 m a.s.l.). The species is able to survive in agroecosystems but remains a localized endemic. As it is not declining listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Mpumalanga: Nelspruit district (Hall & Son Farm) (-25.47, 30.96); Graskop (-24.937, 30.848); Mariepskop State Forest (-23.584, 30.864); Songimvelo Nature Reserve, Diepgezet (-25.937, 31.102).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers sampled from grassland and forest habitats in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011). The type specimens were sampled in avocado orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is able to survive in agroecosystems and is unlikely to be impacted by crop cultivation and forestry plantations. It is protected in two protected areas, Songimvelo Nature Reserve and Mariepskop State Forest.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The female was described by Haddad et al. (2009) and the male by Haddad & Mbo (2017). Abdomen dark grey with cream spots on the dorsal surface.

Austrachelas bergi male and female after Haddad et al. (2009)

Austrachelas entabeni Haddad & Mbo, 2017

COMMON NAME: Entabeni Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described by Haddad & Mbo (2017), from Entabeni Forest. It is presently only known from the type locality (EOO=4 km²; AOO= 4km²; 1360 m a.s.l.). Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Soutpansberg Mountains ca. 20 km N of Levubu, Entabeni Forest (-23.00, 30.23).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers sampled from the Forest Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female (Haddad & Mbo 2017). Abdomen with creamy-grey chevron markings dorsally and V-shaped mediolateral marking ventrally.

Austrachelas entabeni female after Haddad & Mbo (2017).

Austrachelas incertus Lawrence, 1938

COMMON NAME: Eastern Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: VU **NATIONAL CRITERIA:** B1ab (ii,iii)+2ab (ii,iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Lawrence (1938), from Bulwer in KwaZulu-Natal. It is endemic to the province (EOO=4 589 km²; AOO=28 km²; 870-2477 m a.s.l.). Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range and experiencing ongoing decline in habitat outside of protected areas it is therefore listed as Vulnerable.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Bulwer (-29.79, 29.77); Cathedral Peak (-28.96, 29.22); Cathkin Peak (-29.03, 29.40); Hilton (-29.48, 30.30); Karkloof (-29.36, 30.19); Ndumeni Forest (-28.98, 29.23); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.10); Pietermaritzburg (-29.60, 30.38); Wakefield Farm (-29.50, 29.90).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers usually collected in pitfall traps or by litter sifting in the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by infrastructure development around Pietermaritzburg, and crop farming around Hilton and Karkloof.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Haddad *et al.* (2009). Known from both sexes. Abdomen with cream chevron markings.

Austrachelas incertus from Wakefield Photo P. Webb

After Haddad et al. (2009) and Lawrence (1939)

After Haddad et al. (2009)

Female and male after Haddad et al. (2009)

Austrachelas kalaharinus Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009

COMMON NAME: Kalahari Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Haddad et al. (2009) from the type locality, Benfontein Nature Reserve, which borders on the Northern Cape and Free State (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1145 m a.s.l.). Identification of the female is problematic and too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. It is therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 24.82).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers. Specimens were sampled from pitfall traps in the Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male (Haddad et al. 2009). Abdomen cream both laterally and ventrally.

Male after Haddad et al. (2009).

Austrachelas merwei Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009

COMMON NAME: Van der Merwe's Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Haddad et al. (2009) from Ngome State Forest. It is known only from the type locality (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1000 m a.s.l.). This endemic species is protected in the Ngome State Forest but it seems to have a restricted distribution. More sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers. During surveys in the Ngome State forest (Van der Merwe et al. 1999) 37 specimens were collected in pitfall traps in dense forest areas.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: This endemic species is protected in the Ngome State Forest but it seems to have a restricted distribution. More sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad et al. 2009). Abdomen with mottled grey chevron, ventral lacking scutum.

Austrachelas merwei female and male after Haddad et al. (2009).

Austrachelas natalensis Lawrence, 1942

COMMON NAME: Natal Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal Province endemic described by Lawrence (1942), from Estcourt. This species is known from several locations in the KwaZulu-Natal midlands and coastal regions (EOO=7 728 km²; AOO=28 km²; 80-2892 m a.s.l.). This species is able to survive habitat alteration and occurs in agroecosystems, therefore despite having a restricted distribution, it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Estcourt (-29.00, 29.87); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); Pietermaritzburg (-29.60, 30.38); Sani Pass (-29.66, 29.46); Shongweni Dam and Game Reserve (-29.80, 30.74); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.20).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled with pitfall traps and litter sifting from the Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: This species is adaptable to habitat alterations and is able to survive in varied habitat types, including agroecosystems and protected in the Shongweni Dam and Game Reserve and Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Haddad et al. (2009). Known from both sexes. Abdomen with cream chevron marking.

Austrachelas natalensis
Lawrence, 1942

Austrachelas natalensis female Photo ASD

Austrachelas natalensis female and male after Haddad et al. (2009)

Austrachelas pondoensis Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009

COMMON NAME: Pondoland Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Haddad et al. (2009), from Mzimhlava River Mouth (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 10 m a.s.l.) in the Lusikisiki district. The species was locally abundant at the time of collection in 1980. It is likely to be under collected, and may occur in other forest patches along the Wild Coast. More sampling is needed, to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Mzimhlava River Mouth (-31.33, 29.67).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers sampled in coastal evergreen forest in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed, to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad et al. 2009; Ramírez 2014). Abdomen with mottled pale grey chevron.

Austrachelas pondoensis male and female after Haddad et al. (2009)

Austrachelas reavelli Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009

COMMON NAME: Reavell's Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Haddad et al. (2009), with Ngoye Forest the type locality. The species is presently known only from the northern parts of KwaZulu-Natal (EOO<500 km²; AOO=8 km²; 340-634 m a.s.l.). It is, however, under collected, and more sampling is required to determine this species range and any threats occurring outside of protected areas. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Hluhluwe-uMfolozi Game Park (-28.00, 31.72); Ngoye Forest (-28.84, 31.69).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers that were sampled from the Forest and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is only known from two subpopulations that occur in protected areas Ngoye Forest and Hluhluwe-uMfolozi Game Park (Mgobozi et al. 2008). However, under collected, and more sampling is required to determine this species range and any threats occurring outside of protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad et al. 2009). Carapace orange-brown in colour, slightly paler along midline. Abdomen with mottled pale grey chevron.

Male and female of *Austrachelas reavelli* after Haddad et al. (2009)

Austrachelas sexoculata Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009

COMMON NAME: Six-eyed Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Haddad et al. (2009), from East London. The species is only known from type locality (EEO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 68 m a.s.l.) in an area highly transformed for human settlement. However, there has not been a lot of collecting in and around East London. More sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range and current status. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* East London (-33.01, 27.90).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers sampled from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is likely to be threatened by loss of habitat for infrastructure development in East London. It is only known from an old collection in 1916 with no habitat details. More sampling is needed, to collect the female and determine the species' range and current status.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male (Haddad et al. 2009). Carapace deep-red, abdomen dark grey on the dorsal side and cream on the lateral and ventral sides.

Austrachelas sexoculata male after Haddad et al. (2009)

Austrachelas wassenaari Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009

COMMON NAME: Wassenaar's Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: Rare

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Haddad et al. (2009), from Richards Bay. The species is recorded from the northern coastal parts of KwaZulu-Natal, from localities that are about 75 km apart (EOO<100 km²; AOO=8 km²; 4-56 m a.s.l.). Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range it is listed as Rare.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Fanie's Island (-28.10, 32.45); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.83, 32.08).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers. It has been found in rehabilitated coastal dune forests previously mined near Richards Bay, and as a ground dweller it is likely to be able to survive habitat modification (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wassenaar 2002). It falls within the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the iSimangaliso Wetland Park but more sampling needed to determine its range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes, illustrated. Abdomen with chevron markings.

Male and female of *Austrachelas wassenaari* after Haddad et al. (2009)

GENUS *DRASSODELLA* Hewitt, 1916

The genus *Drassodella* Hewitt, 1916 is one of four Afrotropical genera of Gallieniellidae, and is presently represented by 19 species, all endemic to South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Drassodella Long-Jawed Ground Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Drassodella salisburyi* Hewitt, 1916

MORPHOLOGY: Small to medium spiders, body length 2.5–10 mm. Carapace broad, oval; cephalic region slightly narrowed, broadest between coxae II and III; in lateral profile raised evenly along midline, sloping gently posteriorly; eight eyes in two rows (4:4); lateral eyes set on low tubercles; anterior eye row slightly straight or recurved when viewed from front; anterior median eyes smaller or equal to anterior lateral eyes; posterior median eyes flattened, transversely oval, more or less the same distance between each other and PLE; surface smooth, sparsely covered in short straight and feathery setae; usually black, rarely yellow-orange or brown with lateral margins with narrow fringe composed of white feathery setae; fovea short to elongate, narrow; chelicerae usually moderately protruding in males, slightly angled and/or vertically orientated in females. Abdomen oval-elongate, with golden, yellow, white or cream dorsal stripes or spots, or without markings, on black or grey background; dorsum covered in short erect and feathery setae, markings comprising dense feathery setae; dorsum with two pairs of small sigilla, posterior pair more widely separated. Legs long and moderately thin; leg formula 4123; anterior pairs of legs weakly spined, posterior pairs of legs moderately to strongly spined; trochanters notched (Mbo & Haddad 2019).

LIFESTYLE: *Drassodella* are fast-moving ground-dwellers frequently collected under small rocks and stones, in pitfall traps or by litter sifting. They are sometimes encountered in close association with ants (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013; Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad 2014). Pekár et al. (2011) and Pekár & Toft (2015) proposed that the Gallieniellidae consists of stenophagous specialists (having a narrow diet breadth). *Drassodella* are relatively rare spiders endemic to South Africa, and occur in all of the floral biomes except Desert. The highest species richness was found in the Forest and Fynbos biomes (8 spp. each) and the Savanna biome (5 spp.) (Mbo & Haddad 2019).

TAXONOMY: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019).

D. septemmaculata Photo Charles Haddad

D. vascivulva Photo Charles Haddad

D. amatola Photo Charles Haddad

D. quinquelabecula Photo Peter Webb

Drassodella amatola Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Amatola Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Easter Cape endemic described by Mbo & Haddad (2019) from Hogsback (EOO<100 km²; AOO=8 km²; 1013 m a.s.l.). Species known only from a single male and two females. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Amatola Mountains, Hogsback (-32.36, 26.56).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled during litter sifting in Afromontane Forest.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019) and known from both sexes. Abdomen uniform black without markings.

Drassodella amatola after Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella aurostriata Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Golden Striped Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: Rare

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Mbo & Haddad (2019), from the Tsitsikamma National Park. The species is known from several localities around Knysna (EOO = 617 km²; AOO=20 km²; 26-232 m a.s.l.). Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range it is listed as Rare.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Humansdorp, Tsitsikamma National Park, De Vasselot, near Nature's Valley (-33.58, 23.35; George, Groeneweide Forest Station (-33.57, 22.27); Goukamma Nature Reserve, Groenvlei Lake hiking trail (-34.02, 22.33); Gouna and Diepwalle State Forest, North of Knysna (-33.57, 23.02); Knysna, Uitzicht Annex (-34.00, 23.20)

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled with pitfall traps and litter sifting from dry, humid forest and Coastal Forest.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling needed to determine the species' range. Protected in the Tsitsikamma National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Goukamma Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known from both sexes. Recognised by the two golden yellow stripes on the abdomen.

Drassodella aurostriata male and female after Mbo & Haddad, 2019

Drassodella baviaans Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Spotted Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Mbo & Haddad (2019) and known only from the male sampled at Baviaanskloof (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 473 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Baviaanskloof, Keurkloof, Farm Ferndale (-33.41, 24.50).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled with pitfall traps and litter sifting from the Baviaanskloof in the Eastern Cape.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known only from the male recognized by the spots on the dorsal side of the abdomen.

Drassodella baviaans male after Mbo & Haddad, 2019

Drassodella flava Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Yellow Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Mbo & Haddad (2019) from Ngome State Forest. It is known from three provinces (EEO= 11 854 km²; AOO=28km²; 1076-1709 m a.s.l.). Due to wide range listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Vryheid, Ngome State Forest (-27.49, 31.26). *Limpopo:* Forest on Magoebaskloof Trail (-23.49, 29.59). *Mpumalanga:* Berlin Forest Station (-24.50, 30.50), Graskop, God's Window (-24.52, 30.53); Graskop, Window View on R532 (-24.55, 30.50); Graskop area (-24.53, 30.52); Sabie, Bridal Veil Waterfall (-25.04, 30.43).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled with pitfall traps and litter sifting from forest areas. During surveys at Ngome State Forest different habitats were sampled. The species has been sampled from open forest, dense forest, pine plantation and ecotone (Van der Merwe et al. 1996).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. The species is protected in the Ngome State Forest.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019), known from both sexes. Recognized by the yellow to orange legs and carapace.

Drassodella flava male and female after Mbo & Haddad (2019).

Drassodella guttata Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Platberg Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Free State endemic described by Mbo & Haddad (2019) and known only from the type locality Platberg Nature Reserve (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 2188 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient .

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Free State*: Harrismith, Platberg Nature Reserve, Bottom of Donkey Pass (-28.168, 29.120).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled from under rocks on the mountain side in Alpine Grassland.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: It is protected in the Platberg Nature Reserve but some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known from both sexes. The abdomen decorated with white spots.

Drassodella guttata after Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella lotzi Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Lotz's Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic known only from the type locality Enseleni Game Reserve (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 64m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Enseleni Game Reserve, Lower Umfolozi (-28.42, 31.59).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled with pitfall traps and litter sifting.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Enseleni Game Reserve but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known only from female. Abdomen grey-brown in colour, with dotted mottling.

Drassodella lotzi female after Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella maculata Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Sneeu-berg Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Mbo & Haddad (2019) from various localities at the Asante Sana Game Reserve (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1458 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Asante Sana Game Reserve, between Waterkloof and Zuurkloof (-32.17, 24.58).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller. The species were sampled with pitfall traps during a study to collect epigaeic invertebrates at Asante Sana Private Game Reserve in the Sneeu-berg Mountain Complex, part of the Great Escarpment mountain system in southern Africa (Midgley 2012).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Asante Sana Private Game Reserve but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known only from the female that bears white spots on her abdomen dorsally.

Drassodella maculata female Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella melana Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Dark Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Mfongosi in KwaZulu-Natal. It is known from three provinces, including four protected areas (EOO=402 362 km²; AOO=40 km²; 294-1498 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide range and no significant threats it is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Krantzkop (-28.97, 30.86); Mfongosi (-27.28, 32.15); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22); 15 km ENE of Louwsberg on R69 (-27.32, 31.25); Good Hope, Midlands (28.15, 30.42E); Ithala Game Reserve, Ntshodwe Camp (-27.33, 31.17); Jackson's Falls on Mhlatuzana River (-29.48, 30.45); Krantzkloof Nature Reserve (29.46, 30°49'E). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, The Downs (24°08'S, 30°18'E). **Mpumulanga:** Bergvliet Forest Station (-34.03, 18.63); Mariepskop State Forest, Drakensberg (-23.35, 30.51).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers that are mainly sampled in pitfall traps from the Forest and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011). The species is abundant in the Ngome State Forest, where it was mainly sampled from grasslands, but also from indigenous forests and pine plantations (Van der Merwe et al. 1996).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened in parts of its range by silvicultural and agricultural activities; however the overall population is not significantly impacted. It is protected in Ngome State Forest, Ithala Game Reserve, Krantzkloof Nature Reserve and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Abdomen uniformly dark brown.

After Tucker (1923)

Male and female after Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella montana Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Sani Pass Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Mbo & Haddad (2019) and sampled from different elevations on the Sani Pass (EOO<100 km²; AOO=8 km²; 1169 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Sani Pass elevational project, Glen Bain, (-30.03, 29.58); Sani Pass elevation project, Ixopo (-30.11, 30.08).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller. It was sampled with pitfall traps during an elevational project and it was sampled between 900 and 1200 m a.s.l.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known from both sexes. Abdomen black with white speckle above spinnerets.

Drassodella montana after Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella purcelli Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Purcell's Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Matjiesfontein. It is presently known only from a few localities (EOO= 836 km²; AOO=16 km²; 662-969 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.285, 20.407); Matjiesfontein, Farm Jagerskraal (-33.134, 20.248); Matjiesfontein (-33.22, 20.58); Touws River station (-33.20, 20.03).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled with pitfall traps and litter sifting from pitfall traps. At Anysberg Nature Reserve it was sampled from riparian woodland.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed, to collect the male and determine the species' range. It is protected in the Anysberg Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Only female known. Abdomen black with two pair of white spots.

Drassodella purcelli
Tucker, 1923

Drassodella purcelli female after Mbo & Haddad (2019) and Tucker (1923)

Drassodella quinquelabecula Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Western Cape Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Caledon. It is known from several localities (EOO=20 008 km²; AOO=20 km²; 8-588 m a.s.l.). The species is threatened in parts of its range from agricultural practices. Due to its wide geographic range and the fact that is likely to be under collected it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Caledon (-34.13, 19.25); De Hoop Nature Reserve, Potberg, (-34.22, 20.32.48); Knysna, Uitzicht Annex (34.00, 23.20); Swartberg Nature Reserve, Gamkaskloof (-33.21, 21.41); Aardvark Nature Reserve (-33.4941, 21.0880); Matroosberg (-33.42, 19.84).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers sampled with pitfall traps and litter sifting from the Fynbos and Nama Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is protected in De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009), Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and Aardvark Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known from both sexes. Abdomen cream brown with five transverse lines on the dorsal surface.

After Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella quinquelabecula from Aardvark NR
Photo Peter Webb

Drassodella salisburyi Hewitt, 1916

COMMON NAME: Salisbury's Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Hewitt (1916) from Grahamstown, and known from several localities (EOO=28 409 km²; AOO=20 km²; 222-1488 m a.s.l.), The species has a wide enough distribution range for it to be listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Asante Sana Game Reserve, buttress Waterkloof (-32.169, 24.588); Asante Sana Private Game Reserve, Zuurkloof (-32.267, 25.004); Grahamstown (-33,19, 26. 32); Kentani (-32.30, 28.19); Van Stadens Pass (-33.55, 25.13); Great Fish River Reserve, Hermanskraal (-33.07, 26.87).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers sampled in some localities with pitfall traps; recorded from the Thicket, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Fynbos biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are not significant. It is protected in the Asante Sana Private Game Reserve and Great Fish River Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTE: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known from both sexes. They can be recognized by the broad pale median band on the abdomen dorsally.

Drassodella salisburyi male and female after Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella septemmaculata (Strand, 1909)

COMMON NAME: Cape's Northern Long-Jawed Ground Spider / Six-spot Long-Jawed Ground spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Strand (1909) from Signal Hill, Cape Town as *Prothesima septemmaculata*. Known from two provinces (EOO=12 736 km²; AOO=60 km²; 9-1758 m a.s.l.). Due to wide range listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Western Cape:** Bergvliet, Diep River (-34.03, 18.27); Cape Town, Constantia (-34.02, 18.23); Cape Town, Gardens (-33.56, 18.24E); Cape Town, Muizenberg (-34.06, 18.27); Cape Town, Newlands (-33.58, 18.29); Cape Town, Newlands Forest (-33.57, 18.27); Table Mountain National Park, Signal Hill (-33.56, 18.24); Table Mountain National Park, Maclears Beacon (-33.58, 18.25); Table Mountain, ravine below Platteklip (-33.57, 18.25); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Wupperthal, Crystal Pools (-32.27 19.540); Cederberg Wilderness Area, Sneekop (-32.21, 19.09); False Bay, St James (-34.07, 18.27); Fisherhaven (-34.21, 19.07); Great Winterhoek Mountains (-33.08, 19.10); Hout Bay (-34.02, 18.21); Side of Kalk Bay and St James Mountain (-34.08, 18.27); Tulbagh, Piquetberg Road Station (-33.22, 19.07). **Northern Cape:** Oorlogskloof Nature Reserve, Nieuwoudtville (-31.31, 19.26).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers that have been sampled in high numbers with pitfall traps in the Cederberg Wilderness Area. Sampled from the Fynbos and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Species protected in the Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020), Oorlogskloof Nature Reserve and Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016).

9TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Males with thicker dorsal lines than females.

D. septemmaculata Photo Charles Haddad

D. septemmaculata Photo Norman Larsen

After Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella tenebrosa Lawrence, 1938

COMMON NAME: Pietermaritzburg Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: EN

NATIONAL CRITERIA: B1ab(ii,ii)+2ab(ii,iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Lawrence (1938) from Karkloof. Also sampled from two other locations in Pietermaritzburg (EOO<200 km²; AOO=8 km²; 647-1482 m a.s.l.). There is ongoing loss of habitat to urban expansion, crop cultivation and plantation forestry, this species therefore qualifies for Endangered under Criterion B.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Karkloof (29.19, 30.15); Pietermaritzburg (-29.37, 30.23); KwaZulu-Natal Botanical Gardens (-29.36, 30.20); Pietermaritzburg, Town Bush (-29.36, 30.23).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by loss of habitat to crop farming, plantation forestry and urbanization. More sampling needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known from both sexes. Females with grey-yellow abdomen while males have grey abdomen.

Drassodella tenebrosa
Lawrence, 1938

Drassodella tenebrosa after Mbo & Haddad (2019).

Drassodella tolkien Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Tolkien's Long-Jawed Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Mbo & Haddad (2019) from Hogsback, Amatola Forestry Company (EOO<100 km²; AOO=8 km²; 1203-1220 m a.s.l.). It is only known from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Amatola Mountains, Hogsback, Amatola Forestry Company (-32.37, 26.58).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled with pitfall traps in Fynbos biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known from both sexes. Abdomen dark brown with four white dorsal posterolateral markings.

Drassodella tolkien after Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella transversa Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Mpumalanga Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: Rare

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Mpumalanga endemic species described by Mbo & Haddad (2019) from Blyde River Canyon. The species has also been sampled from Limpopo (EOO= 2026 km²; AOO=12 km²; 396-1942 m a.s.l.). Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range it is listed as Rare.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa .

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Mpumalanga: Blyde River Canyon, Bourke's Luck Pot-holes (-25.09, 30.46); Dullstroom, Groblers Farm (-25.29, 30.05); Mariepskop State Forest, Drakensberg (-23.35, 30.51),

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled with pitfall traps and litter sifting from the Forest and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats but some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known from both sexes. Female abdomens black with six white feathery spots and male with two pairs of white spots with posterior one link with white band.

Drassodella transversa after Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella trilineata Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Three-striped Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Mbo & Haddad (2019) and known only from the type locality Baviaanskloof (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 473 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Keurkloof, Farm Ferndale, Baviaanskloof (-33.45, 24.48).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled during litter sifting from Afromontane forest.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Known only from the female and it can be recognized by a narrow white median carapace stripe and pair of narrow white dorsolateral abdominal stripes.

Drassodella trilineata after Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella vasivulva Tucker, 1923

COMMON NAME: Cape's Southern Long-Jawed Ground Spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Tucker (1923) from Knysna. Known from a few localities (EOO=10 351 km²; AOO=24 km²; 2-414 m a.s.l.). The species has a broad distribution in the southern parts of the Western Cape and may be locally abundant it is also likely to be under collected, therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Cape Town, Muizenberg (-34.06, 18.27); De Hoop Nature Reserve, Koppie Alleen (-34.29, 20.30); De Hoop Nature Reserve, Potberg (-34.23, 20.32); De Hoop Nature Reserve, Lekkerwater road (-34.24, 20.33); Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve, Kogelberg Valley (-34.20, 18.57); Moordkuil Valley (-34.04, 22.07).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled from leaf litter in the Forest and Fynbos biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in two protected areas: De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009) and Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes., Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). The thickness of the dorsal lines more or less the same in both sexes.

Drassodella vasivulva Photo Charles Haddad

Female and male after Mbo & Haddad (2019)

Drassodella venda Mbo & Haddad, 2019

COMMON NAME: Venda Long-Jawed Ground Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: Rare

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described by Mbo & Haddad (2019) from Entabeni Nature Reserve (EOO= 2026 km²; AOO=12 km²; 1360 m a.s.l.). The species has been collected from a few localities in the province. Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range it is listed as Rare.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Venda, Soutpansberg, Entabeni Nature Reserve (-22.59, 30.16); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Haffenden Heights (-24.06, 30.10); Soutpansberg, Thathe Vondo Forest (-22.50, 30.21)

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller sampled with pitfall traps and litter sifting from the Savanna and Forest Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Protected in the Entabeni Nature Reserve, Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve and Thathe Vondo Forest.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Mbo & Haddad (2019). Both sexes known and they can be recognized by their genitalia and the dark brown carapace and black abdomen without markings.

Drassodella venda male and female after Mbo & Haddad (2019).

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